

Creative Writing (Writing Poem) Course In Liberal Studies: Implementation And Implications

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 14, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: July 19, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Liberal Studies Cluster, Students, Lecturers, Creativity, Implementations And Implications</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12779174</p>	<p><i>The Centre for the Promotion of Knowledge and Language Learning, UMS was founded to offer liberal studies courses in UMS. There are three components in the liberal studies clusters offered in UMS; they are Effective Communication and Basic Career, Critical Thinking and Malaysian Ethos, and Current Malaysian and International Issues. Creative Writing is one the courses offered under the Effective Communication and Basic Career cluster. The objective of course is to expose students to creative writing skills. It is offered to all UMS students except students from the Arts Programme in the Faculty of Humanities, Arts and Heritage. It is taught by one lecturer; students are divided into three sections with each section consisting of 60 students. The expected outcome of this course is that students should be able to write and to use those skills as part of their career. Given the short duration, students are only taught writing for literature, with a focus on writing poems. Students are guided and then expected to produce their own works. This study focused on how the course was conducted, its challenges and implications on students and the lecturer teaching the course. A total of 151 students who had taken this course completed questionnaires. Science stream students perceived that this course was not useful to them in terms of knowledge, problem solving and life-long learning. One lecturer teaching in multiple sessions and the high student numbers caused burden to the lecturer and resulted in unequal learning experience for the students.</i></p>

Introduction

Liberal studies in the West are not new but in developing countries such as Malaysia it is a rather new system of education. Liberal studies are only offered in the National University of Malaysia (*Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*) and University Malaysia Sabah (UMS). These two universities differ in how they offer liberal studies. In the National University, liberal studies are known as general studies.

The Centre for the Promotion of Knowledge and Language Learning in UMS was founded together with UMS in 1994. It offers courses which are compulsory for all university students, electives and languages. The purpose of offering the Liberal Studies Cluster is to expose students to knowledge other than those taught in their own Faculties.

The Liberal Studies Cluster contains three components. They are Effective Communication and Basic Career (UC), Critical Thinking and Malaysian Ethos (UE), and Current Malaysian and International Issues (UK). Every undergraduate student must take one course from each component and obtain a pass. If students failed the course, they must either retake the same course or take a different course offered under the same component. A student who received a grade of C- or lower, may also retake the course.

Courses offered in the UC component are Communication Skills, Negotiation Skills, Creative Writing and Organizational Management. The course code for Creative Writing is UC 01702. For the UE component, examples of courses offered are Ethics and Morality, Literature and Gender, Foundation in Philosophy, Inter Faith Dialogue, and Critical Thinking. For the UK component, students may choose among courses such as the Malaysian Constitution, Current Political Thinking, Law and Society, and Food and Nutrition.

Method

A random sample of students (n=151) who have completed the Creative Writing course were asked to give their thoughts and responses in a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire covered aspects of perception about the course, comprehension, characteristics of creative writing and course implementation. All respondents were contacted via social media. Social media was used because communication was carried out via social media throughout the course implementation. Statistical analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics version 21.

Writing and creativity

Writing is essentially not an easy task. It requires a long time. Creative writing requires an able mind and body, interest, a deep passion and a high self discipline; talent is a bonus (Hizairi, 1996: ix). Writing requires individuals to be more sensitive to their environment, to possess high reasoning abilities, and to be creative. When writing, individuals are intentionally seeking, creating and introducing problems. These problems would then have to be addressed and resolved by the authors themselves. Therefore it is up to the students' efforts, whether they are willing to endure the hardship over the period of the creative writing course to learn to write. This study aims to examine the implementation of a creative writing course as an elective course opened to students from various fields of study in UMS.

Creative comes from the Latin word, 'creare', which means 'to make' or 'to create'. Many experts define creativity as "production of something new, original," and involves the use of imagination and exploration, the process of change, development and evolution in management of life, and it is subjective. (Tield, 1976:1; Ainon and Abdullah, 1994; Kneller, 1965; Abdul Ghaffar, 1963; Roger, 1970; Meer & Stain, 1955). Creativity is the ability to produce something using thought and imagination to produce something new, creative, of quality, and is useful (Jauhara Hj. Tak, 1995).

The root of creativity is the willingness to create, ability to create or ability to produce a new combination. Creativity in literature is borne of an urging from the situation and the desire for someone to showcase his / her true potential. Many science students perceived that the creative writing course was not useful to them. Significantly higher number of science students said that the creative writing course did not widen their knowledge, did not train them in problem solving, did not inculcate positive values, and did not encourage life-long learning ($p < 0.05$), see Table 1.

Table 1: Perception of students from different disciplines on various statements regarding the creative writing course.

Statement tested	Faculty			Fisher's exact test, p value	
	Science	Arts & Humanities			
The creative writing course widens my knowledge	Disagree	n	23	1	0.009*
		row %	96%	4%	
		col %	20%	3%	
	Agree	n	90	37	
		row %	71%	29%	
		col %	80%	97%	
The creative writing course trains me to think creatively	Disagree	n	18	2	0.106
		row %	90%	10%	
		col %	16%	5%	
	Agree	n	95	36	
		row %	73%	28%	
		col %	84%	95%	
The creative writing course trains me in problem solving	Disagree	n	37	5	0.021*
		row %	88%	12%	
		col %	33%	13%	
	Agree	n	76	33	
		row %	70%	30%	
		col %	67%	87%	
The creative writing course inculcates positive values	Disagree	n	17	1	0.044*
		row %	94%	6%	
		col %	15%	3%	
	Agree	n	96	37	
		row %	72%	28%	
		col %	85%	97%	
The creative writing	Disagree	n	25	4	0.154

course trains me to think critically		row %	86%	14%	
		col %	22%	11%	
	Agree	n	88	34	
		row %	72%	28%	
The creative writing course encourages the ability to practise life-long learning	Disagree	n	32	4	0.028*
		row %	89%	11%	
		col %	28%	11%	
	Agree	n	81	34	
		row %	70%	30%	
		col %	72%	90%	

* significant at $p < 0.05$.

Course Implementation

At the Centre for Knowledge Promotion and Language Learning, UMS, every course is divided into three sections. Each section consists a minimum of 60 students and a maximum of 80 students. The university's main time table has allocated two time slots for courses offered by the Centre, which are 11 a.m. to 1 p.m. and 7 to 9 p.m. Most students (125 respondents, 83%) who took this course were happy with these schedule. However 26 students (17%) were unhappy with these schedule because the environment at that time were not conducive for their creative thought process. Lecturers teaching such courses have the flexibility to choose whether to teach during the day or in the evening. Each section is allocated two hours teaching time. Therefore lecturers teaching courses offered under the Liberal Studies Cluster teach a total of six hours for three sections in a week. Total number of students is 180 to 240.

Teaching and Learning Process

The syllabus for the Creative Writing course is designed to expose students to techniques and styles in creative writing. The course write-up is available in the prospectus. Therefore potential students know that it is a basic level class, which imparts information about writing techniques and trains them to produce creative writing. Other than creative writing, the course also exposes students to creative thinking skills. Students are exposed to the concept of creative thinking, how to think creatively through the creative thought processes, the attempts involved in starting to write creatively, and general information about literature. Students are guided to eliminate feelings of "do not know", "do not want to", "not creative", "no talent", which can block their creative process. Students are exposed to formats and characteristics present in works such as prose, poem and short drama. These elements will be discussed in detail during classes to allow students to use the information to produce a creative work.

The syllabus includes several individual writing assignments, and grouped assignments in the form of creating and staging a short drama. One group typically consists of 6 to 8 students. There is a written final exam at the end of the semester, which is conducted under exam conditions in a formal setting. By the eighth week of a 14-week semester, students will focus on the practical sessions. Students will be exposed to the environment around them as part of encouraging the creative process. For example, students from sections conducted in the late evenings will be brought outside the classroom to observe the night scenes. Likewise students from the day sections will be brought out of the classroom, assembled into groups and left to observe and take in the environment at that time.

Course assessments are 40 percent for stories (20 percent for poems and 20 percent for short stories), 30 percent for staging a drama or producing a short video, and 30 percent for the final exam. The lectures do not contain indepth literary concepts and theory, given that this is a basic level course and opened to students from all disciplines.

The course is taught in the Malay language and all assignments are done in the same language. Malay is the mother tongue of most people who identify as Malays. All Malaysians of all ethnic origin learn the language in school as it is the national language. However fluency and ability to write creatively among non-Malay students are usually lower than Malay students. Exceptions occur for individuals who are polyglots and / or interested in Malay literature. However, there is no significant association between level of fluency in the Malay language and perception of difficulty level of the creative writing curriculum (X^2 test, $p=0.354$, see Table 2). There was also no association in perception of difficulty level of the course between male and female students (X^2 test, $p=0.232$).

There was a perception among science students that they would not do well in creative writing. Surprisingly, significantly more Arts and Humanities students perceived the curriculum as difficult (X^2 test, $p=0.043$), see Table 3.

Table 2: Perception of difficulty level of creative writing course by students of various fluency levels in the Malay language.

Ethnic group by usual fluency levels in Malay language	Curriculum of creative writing course is very difficult	
	Disagree (n=69)	Agree (n=82)
Malay (n=67), mother tongue fluency	31	36
Sabah & Sarawak indigenous groups (n=40), mother tongue or close to mother tongue fluency	18	22
Chinese and Indian (n=29), non-mother tongue, learnt formally in school	16	13
Others (n=15), fluency of Malay cannot be determined	4	11

X^2 test, $p=0.354$

Table 3: Perception of difficulty level of creative writing course by students enrolled in science versus arts and humanities faculties.

Faculty	Curriculum of creative writing course is very difficult	
	Disagree (n=69)	Agree (n=82)
Science (n=113)	57	56
Arts and Humanities (n=38)	12	26

X^2 test, $p=0.043$

Writing poetry

In Malay, poetry and poems are called *poem*, from the Dutch word, *poesi*. This modern terminology was borrowed from the Dutch by the Indonesians to mean compositions in stanzas where being poetic, melodious, having rhymes in syllables and choice of words are important (Kassim Ahmad, 1960; Nurazmi Kuntum, 1991; Zaaba, 1965). *Poemis* now popular and ingrained in the Malay world. The Malay definitive dictionary, *Kamus Dewan Bahasa*, gives *poem* as a composition which is poetic (such as *syair*, *pantun*, etc.) *Poem* has parts which rhyme, is bound by certain rules and prioritises beauty and imagination to portray the truth. *Poem* is now also known as *sajak*.

Waluyo (2003:1) states that *poem* is a literary work using language which is compacted, shortened, is given rhyming properties, and uses imaginative metaphorical choice of words. The author does not explain in detail what is expressed, unless otherwise indicated. He/she only mentions the main point or what he/she feels or opines as important (Suharianto, 2005:35). Thus *poem* is a result of the outpouring of the author about something that he/she feels, sees, or thinks; written or rendered through carefully arranged rhyming words which are packed with meaning. Coolidge states that *poem* is “the best words arranged in the best manner.”

The fact that the teaching and learning process were effective can be proven with data. If the students had not benefited from the course, those who perceived the curriculum as difficult would be expected to find their comprehension of *poem* limited due to lack of mastery of the Malay language. However data showed that those students who perceived the course as difficult, found that they understood more about *poem* after attending the course. This association was statistically significant for the Sabah and Sarawak indigenous groups and those who were listed as ‘other ethnic groups’ (see Table 4).

Table 4: Association between perception of difficulty of creative writing course and comprehension of poem

Ethnic group by usual fluency levels in Malay language	Curriculum of creative	After attending the creative writing course, I understood more about	After attending the creative writing course, I understood more about

	writing course is very difficult	<i>poem</i>			short stories		
		Disagree	Agree	p-value	Disagree	Agree	p-value
Malay, mother tongue fluency	Disagree	6	25	0.495	7	24	0.322
	Agree	4	32		4	32	
Sabah & Sarawak indigenous groups, mother tongue or close to mother tongue fluency	Disagree	7	11	0.014*	6	12	0.033*
	Agree	1	21		1	21	
Chinese and Indian, non-mother tongue, learnt formally in school	Disagree	9	7	0.130	7	9	0.130
	Agree	3	10		2	11	
Others, fluency of Malay cannot be determined	Disagree	4	0	0.001*	3	1	0.033*
	Agree	0	11		1	10	

* Fisher's exact test significant at $p < 0.05$. Cross-tabulation of perception of difficulty level of curriculum by
- perception of comprehension of *poem* after attending the course, and
- perception of comprehension of short stories after attending the course.

Teaching formation of words in *poem* and short stories: usage of metaphors

Language provides a continuity in human history. Languages are not mere tools for communication. Through languages, humanity built lives because at every moment, we work with languages. Languages, both spoken and written, are conveyors of thoughts, hopes and meanings. The best way to convey them are by associating them with something concrete, or commonly identifiable and comprehensible phenomena, and to do that using the beauty of languages. Usage of metaphors, personifications, similes, comparisons, idioms, and *pantun* reflect the linguistic creativity of writers.

Metaphors are used in everyday conversations without being realised by speakers (Asmah Haji Omar, 2008). Lakoff and Johnson (2003:3) opined that metaphors are present in our everyday lives, in language, thought and behaviour. The way we think and act are based on metaphors. Metaphors are used to convey thoughts, feelings, indirect and polite actions. Metaphors can also teach listeners to think about the real meaning behind what is spoken or written. Students were encouraged to use metaphors in their *poem*.

In this paper, the metaphors discussed here are those used in poems and short stories. Metaphors are used to express poetic imagination. Arrangement and choice of words in poems, combined with suitable metaphors, are testaments of creativity. In other words, the language used in creative language is a figurative language. The following sentences were used to demonstrate metaphors to students.

1. Saya *tidak ada masa* untuk diluahkan bersamamu. / I *don't have the time to give* you.
2. Bagaimana kau *menghabiskan masamu*?/How do you *spend your time* these days?
3. *Banyak waktu* saya berikan untuknya. /I've *invested* a lot of time in her.
4. Saya *tidak cukup* masa. / I don't *have enough* time to spare for that.
5. Anda telah hampir *kehabisan masa*. Anda *perlu atur* masa anda. /You're *running out* of time. You need to *budget* your time.
6. *Luangkan* masa untuk pingpong. / *Put aside* some time for ping pong.
7. Adakah ia berbaloi? Adakah kau masih *punya waktu*?/Is that worth your while? Do you *have much* time left?
8. Kau tidak *menggunakan masa* dengan sebaiknya. /You don't *use* your time profitably.
9. Saya *kehilangan banyak masa* sewaktu terlantar sakit. /I *lost a lot* of time when I got sick.
10. Terima kasih *kerana meluangkan masa*. /Thank you *for your time*.

The word 'time' can be interpreted in many ways and situations. Time is like gold, time is treated like a limited resource, and invaluable. All these are metaphoric concepts that can be used as examples. It is used in everyday life and is associated with a priceless item, money, or limited resources (adapted from Lakoff & Johnson, 2003).

After introducing students to metaphors and what could be connected to them, students were exposed to three basic methods of writing poems (*poem*) and short stories.

The first method is the root word technique. Words were chosen based on root words. Students were asked to come up with metaphors based on words given to them. For example, the word *malam* for night. Words that follow night are *gelap* (dark), *sunyi* (lonely), *sepi* (lonely), *takut* (afraid), *kelam* (dark), *pekat* (dark), *rindu* (longing), *sejuk* (cold), *mengantuk* (sleepy), *bulan* (moon), *bintang* (stars), *pungguk* (owl), etc. Once students have come up with these words, they were shown how to arrange these words to form a metaphor in a poem. The poems written were based on the emotion of students at that particular moment.

The second method is to describe what you see and feel. For example a description of what one could see:

Dedaun nan hijau (Green leaves)
Melambai perlahan (Waving slowly)

It is followed by injecting emotions into a work. Students are shown how an emotion is weaved into the metaphor. For example, to put in emotions:

Dedaun yang hijau melambai (Green leaves waving)
Menggamit rinduku pada yang jauh* (Calling for my longing for the one who is far away)

*The Malay word *menggamit* is associated with calling for someone by gesturing up and down with a palm or hand. It is evoked by the sight of leaves waving, bobbing up and down in the wind.

The third method is to form the beginning, content, and ending. During the practical session, students were given a situation or mood, and asked to note down all their feelings regarding that situation, and to connect them to metaphors from nature. Students worked in small groups. For example, one group was asked to describe a happy and cheerful occasion, another group was asked to describe a sad and sombre event, etc.

Implications and effects

The lecturer observed the following developments in students throughout the course implementation.

1. The practice sessions on word formation and choice of words contributed to expanding the students' ability to think and use metaphors; 82 percent of students reported that they better understood figurative language after attending the course.
2. The improvement process challenged the students to identify common mistakes in writing and avoid waffling. It also trained students to edit their works and finally produce a better piece.
3. Students responded very well because they benefited from the lectures and practicals. Besides understanding the concepts and theories and practising them, they could incorporate them in their everyday lives. Most students who signed up for this course had never or did not know how to vocalise an idea. That process and the subsequent editing exercise gave a big impact to the students; 73 percent of students said that they could express themselves after attending this course.
4. There are students from this course who have gone on to become writers or write as a hobby. Some have gone on to send their works to newspapers and magazines.
5. The lecturer became more creative in teaching creative writing.

At the end of the course, students were asked to evaluate their abilities to write poems, short stories and act. The majority of students indicated that they could write and act after attending the course, see Table 5.

Table 5: Students' ability to write creatively after attending this course.

Statement		n	(%)
After attending the creative writing course, I could write poems	Disagree very much	2	(1)
	Disagree	9	(6)
	Disagree slightly	28	(19)
	Agree	75	(50)
	Agree very much	37	(25)
After attending the creative writing course, I could write short stories	Disagree very much	4	(3)
	Disagree	14	(9)

	Disagree slightly	28 (19)
	Agree	60 (40)
	Agree very much	45 (30)
After attending the creative writing course, I could act	Disagree very much	4 (3)
	Disagree	12 (8)
	Disagree slightly	31 (21)
	Agree	65 (43)
	Agree very much	39 (26)

Challenges and problems

Throughout conducting this course, the following problems created challenges to both the lecturer and students.

1. Disruptions occurred during class. The environment inside and outside the classroom did not give much inspiration to students. One third of students (33.7 percent) reported that facilities, such as the lecture classroom was not suitable.
 - a. Some students (17 percent) found that the afternoon class, 11 a.m. to 1 p.m., and the evening class, 7 to 9 pm, did not allow them a conducive environment to be creative. The outside environment at noon was too hot, and during the evening was too dark with many mosquitoes. The air-conditioning in the classroom in the evening was also too cold.
 - b. Students found that they could not think of much metaphors during the dark and cold evening class schedule.
 - c. Students could not be sent out to explore their environment during the noon class schedule because of the heat.
2. The lecturer did not have enough time to read all the students' poems within the stipulated time of one week. A section had about 60 to 80 students, giving a total of 180 to 240 students per lecturer. This resulted in the lecturer working through the night and during weekends to read all the students' submissions in order to give them feedback before the next batch of new poems were submitted for grading the following week.
3. Students said that they did not have adequate opportunity to discuss with the lecturer. More than half, 53 percent of students reported this.

Conclusion

The creative writing course in the Effective Communication and Basic Career cluster of Liberal Studies is a platform to expose and train students to write creatively. Creative writing is a skill that is useful in the students' future career, increase their competencies, and could possibly be a hobby. This course encouraged students to write from their experience and emotions, and therefore help to develop their thought process. To be more effective, the course scheduling should be improved to create a more conducive environment for students to think creatively. The number of students per lecturer should be reduced to allow for more quality feedback and more access to lecturer per student.

References

- Ainon Mohd & Abdullah Hasan. 1996. *Seni Berfikir Kreatif*. Kuala Lumpur: Utusan Publication & Distributors Sdn.Bhd.
- AOK Hadimadja. (1981). *Seni Mengarang*. Jakarta: Pustaka Jaya.
- Asmiaty Amat. (2012). *MQA Kursus Penulisan Kreatif*. Pusat Penataran Ilmu dan Bahasa, Universiti Malaysia Sabah.
- Asmiaty Amat. (2013). *Modul Kursus Penulisan Kreatif*. UMS: Sekolah Pendidikan Pendidikan.

- Graeme Harper & Jeri Kroll(ed).2007. *Creative Writing Studies: Practice, Research and Pedagogy*, United Kingdom: Multilingual Matters Limited.
- Hizairi Othman. (1996). *Kreativiti dalam Penciptaan Karya Sastera*. Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka.
- Keraf, Gorys.(1994). *Diksi dan Gaya Bahasa*.Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Maimunah Osman. 2005. *Pemikiran Kreatif*. Kuala Lumpur : Institut Tadbiran
- Pradopo, Rahmat Djoko. (1994). *Stilistika dalam Buletin Humaniora No.1 tahun 1994*.Yogyakarta: Fakultas Sastra UGM.
- Rahman Shaari. (1993). *Memahami Gaya Bahasa*. Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka.
- Rahman Shaari. (1990). *Persediaan Menulis Sajak*. Kuala Lumpur: DBP.
- Rene Wellek& Austin Warren, *Theory of Literature* (Translated by Wong Seng Tong). (1988). Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa & Pustaka.
- Teeuw, A., *Sastera & Ilmu Sastera*. (1988). Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa & Pustaka
- George Lakoff and Mark Johnsen (2003). *Metaphors we live by*. London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Lim Swee Tin. (2014). *Penulisan Puisi. Kreativiti, Praktis& Diskusi*. (Buku 1). Kuala Lumpur: Utusan Publication

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